

Table S1. Descriptive statistics of animals used across research fields in Spain (2009–2013).

Field	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Median
Diagnosis of diseases	46594.8	4991.1007	39938	54015	46349
Education and training	15394.4	779.0974	14362	16083	15799
Fundamental biology studies	650850.6	239002.5738	468269	949032	482280
Others	34118.0	3716.2515	28079	37858	34175
Production and quality control of medical and dental products and instruments	41336.8	10367.4478	31460	56905	36216
Production and quality control of veterinary products and instruments	49271.8	15815.9816	33385	72299	43264
Research and development of medical, dental, and veterinary products and instruments	166035.8	5754.0805	160498	175075	165230
Safety evaluations	92225.6	27417.2672	69255	127713	75222

Figure S1. Normality evaluation: histograms and q-q plots of animals across research fields in Spain (2009–2013).

Table S2. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction, assessing differences in the number of animals used across research fields in Spain (2009–2013).

group1	group2	statistic	p	p.adj	p.adj. signif
Disease_diagnosis	Education_training	-2.1640071	3.046380e-02	8.529865e-01	ns
Disease_diagnosis	Fundamental_biology	2.5697585	1.017694e-02	2.849544e-01	ns
Disease_diagnosis	Medical_production	-0.5680519	5.699997e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Disease_diagnosis	Medical_research	1.8935062	5.829058e-02	1.000000e+00	ns
Disease_diagnosis	Others	-1.1631538	2.447671e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Disease_diagnosis	Safety_evaluations	1.1902039	2.339663e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Disease_diagnosis	Veterinary_production	-0.1352504	8.924139e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Education_training	Fundamental_biology	4.7337656	2.203923e-06	6.170983e-05	****
Education_training	Medical_production	1.5959553	1.104988e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Education_training	Medical_research	4.0575134	4.959798e-05	1.388743e-03	**
Education_training	Others	1.0008533	3.168977e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Education_training	Safety_evaluations	3.3542110	7.959163e-04	2.228566e-02	*
Education_training	Veterinary_production	2.0287567	4.248308e-02	1.000000e+00	ns
Fundamental_biology	Medical_production	-3.1378103	1.702150e-03	4.766020e-02	*
Fundamental_biology	Medical_research	-0.6762522	4.988805e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Fundamental_biology	Others	-3.7329123	1.892785e-04	5.299799e-03	**
Fundamental_biology	Safety_evaluations	-1.3795545	1.677238e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Fundamental_biology	Veterinary_production	-2.7050089	6.830256e-03	1.912472e-01	ns
Medical_production	Medical_research	2.4615581	1.383350e-02	3.873380e-01	ns
Medical_production	Others	-0.5951020	5.517753e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Medical_production	Safety_evaluations	1.7582558	7.870400e-02	1.000000e+00	ns
Medical_production	Veterinary_production	0.4328014	6.651590e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Medical_research	Others	-3.0566601	2.238179e-03	6.266903e-02	ns
Medical_research	Safety_evaluations	-0.7033023	4.818674e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Medical_research	Veterinary_production	-2.0287567	4.248308e-02	1.000000e+00	ns
Others	Safety_evaluations	2.3533577	1.860473e-02	5.209323e-01	ns
Others	Veterinary_production	1.0279034	3.039953e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Safety_evaluations	Veterinary_production	-1.3254544	1.850205e-01	1.000000e+00	ns

Table S3. Descriptive statistics of animals used across disease models in Spain (2009–2013).

Field	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Median
Human cancer (excluding carcinogenic risk evaluations)	149847.8	16653.469	126380	173202	14881
Human cardiovascular diseases	42754.0	6852.513	35871	53358	39841
Human nervous and mental disorders	115757.4	5968.679	108086	124712	114967
Other human diseases	190614.0	8135.638	182196	202485	188866
Specific studies of animal diseases	38926.6	5785.187	33932	45363	35853

Figure S2. Normality evaluation: histograms and q-q plots of animals across disease models in Spain (2009–2013).

Table S4. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction, assessing differences in disease models in Spain (2009–2013).

group1	group2	statistic	p	p.adj	p.adj. signif
Animal_diseases	Human_cancer	2.9647156	3.029629e-03	0.0302962889	*
Animal_diseases	Human_cardiovascular_diseases	0.5585696	5.764555e-01	1.0000000000	ns
Animal_diseases	Nervous_disorders	1.8905433	5.868534e-02	0.5868533960	ns
Animal_diseases	Other_human_diseases	4.0388879	5.370522e-05	0.0005370522	***
Human_cancer	Cardiovascular	-2.4061460	1.612182e-02	0.1612182127	ns
Human_cancer	Nervous_disorders	-1.0741723	2.827455e-01	1.0000000000	ns
Human_cancer	Other_human_diseases	1.0741723	2.827455e-01	1.0000000000	ns
Human_cardiovascular_diseases	Nervous_disorders	1.3319737	1.828688e-01	1.0000000000	ns
Human_cardiovascular_diseases	Other_human_diseases	3.4803183	5.008184e-04	0.0050081842	**
Nervous_disorders	Other_human_diseases	2.1483446	3.168639e-02	0.3168638854	ns

Table S5. Descriptive statistics of animal uses across research fields in Spain (2014–2023).

Field	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Median
Basic research	374343.4	5.416180e+04	313197	448149	368572.0
Forensic investigations	0.1	3.162278e-01	0	1	0.0
Higher education or training for the acquisition, maintenance or improvement of professional skills	9386.3	3.382675e+03	2201	13994	9627.5
Maintenance of colonies of genetically altered animals not used in other procedures	34858.9	1.796262e+04	8302	71854	31616.0
Protection of the natural environment in the interest of human or animal health or wellbeing	17333.7	3.600986e+04	661	119045	5090.5
Regulatory use and routine production	146471.3	3.649972e+04	97536	229606	135050.0
Species preservation	486.4	3.012187e+02	13	1043	459.0
Translational and applied research	349042.7	2.499088e+05	6245	792992	272674.5

Figure S3. Normality evaluation: histograms and q-q plots of animal uses across research fields in Spain (2014–2023).

Table S6. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction, assessing differences in the animal uses across research fields in Spain (2014–2023).

group1	group2	statistic	p	p.adj	p.adj. signif
Basic_research	Forensic_investigations	-6.4516166	1.106633e-10	3.098571e-09	****
Basic_research	Higher_education_or_training_for_the_acquisition_maintenance_or_improvement_of_professional_skills	-3.6880137	2.260115e-04	6.328322e-03	**
Basic_research	Maintenance_of_colonies_of_genetically_altered_animals_not_used_in_other_procedures	-2.6865687	7.219010e-03	2.021323e-01	ns
Basic_research	Protection_of_the_natural_environment_in_the_interest_of_human_or_animal_health_or_wellbeing	-4.1309605	3.612507e-05	1.011502e-03	**
Basic_research	Regulatory_use_and_routine_production	-1.5117967	1.305856e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Basic_research	Species_preservation	-5.4598009	4.766688e-08	1.334673e-06	****
Basic_research	Translational_and_applied_research	-0.7221959	4.701741e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Forensic_investigations	Higher_education_or_training_for_the_acquisition_maintenance_or_improvement_of_professional_skills	2.7636029	5.716706e-03	1.600678e-01	ns
Forensic_investigations	Maintenance_of_colonies_of_genetically_altered_animals_not_used_in_	3.7650479	1.665172e-04	4.662480e-03	**

	other_procedures				
Forensic_investigations	Protection_of_the_natural_environment_in_the_interest_of_human_or_a	2.3206561	2.030541e-02	5.685515e-01	ns
Forensic_investigations	Regulatory_use_and_routine_production	4.9398199	7.819477e-07	2.189454e-05	****
Forensic_investigations	Species_preservation	0.9918157	3.212874e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Forensic_investigations	Translational_and_applied_research	5.7294207	1.007742e-08	2.821677e-07	****
Higher_education_or_training_for_the_acquisition_maintenance_or_improvement_of_professional_skills	Maintenance_of_colonies_of_genetically_altered_animals_not_used_in_other_procedures	1.0014450	3.166117e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Higher_education_or_training_for_the_acquisition_maintenance_or_improvement_of_professional_skills	Protection_of_the_natural_environment_in_the_interest_of_human_or_animal_health_or_wellbeing	-0.4429468	6.578042e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Higher_education_or_training_for_the_acquisition_maintenance_or_improvement_of_professional_skills	Regulatory_use_and_routine_production	2.1762169	2.953904e-02	8.270932e-01	ns
Higher_education_or_training_for_the_acquisition_maintenance_or_improvement_of_professional_skills	Species_preservation	-1.7717872	7.642988e-02	1.000000e+00	ns
Higher_education_or_training_for_the_acquisition_maintenance_or_improvement_of_professional_skills	Translational_and_applied_research	2.9658178	3.018793e-03	8.452620e-02	ns
Maintenance_of_colonies_of_geneticall	Protection_of_the_natural_e	-1.4443918	1.486288e-01	1.000000e+00	ns

y_altered_animals_not_used_in_other_procedures	nvironment_in_the_interest_of_human_or_animal_health_or_wellbeing				
Maintenance_of_colonies_of_genetically_altered_animals_not_used_in_other_procedures	Regulatory_use_and_routine_production	1.1747720	2.400860e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Maintenance_of_colonies_of_genetically_altered_animals_not_used_in_other_procedures	Species_preservation	-2.7732322	5.550250e-03	1.554070e-01	ns
Maintenance_of_colonies_of_genetically_altered_animals_not_used_in_other_procedures	Translational_and_applied_research	1.9643728	4.948687e-02	1.000000e+00	ns
Protection_of_the_natural_environment_in_the_interest_of_human_or_animal_health_or_wellbeing	Regulatory_use_and_routine_production	2.6191638	8.814562e-03	2.468077e-01	ns
Protection_of_the_natural_environment_in_the_interest_of_human_or_animal_health_or_wellbeing	Species_preservation	-1.3288404	1.839006e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Protection_of_the_natural_environment_in_the_interest_of_human_or_animal_health_or_wellbeing	Translational_and_applied_research	3.4087646	6.525777e-04	1.827217e-02	*
Regulatory_use_and_routine_production	Species_preservation	-3.9480042	7.880543e-05	2.206552e-03	**
Regulatory_use_and_routine_production	Translational_and_applied_research	0.7896008	4.297609e-01	1.000000e+00	ns
Species_preservation	Translational_and_applied_research	4.7376050	2.162588e-06	6.055246e-05	****

Table S7. Descriptive statistics of animal uses across disease models in Spain (2014–2023).

Field	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Median
Animal diseases	43914.4	17145.197981	18	60105	48220.5
Animal welfare	37029.4	66954.492431	8	222793	14792.0
Disease diagnosis	4489.9	3176.674447	4	9833	3664.5
Human cancer	55872.3	33872.873073	46	116595	49564.0
Human cardiovascular diseases	6541.8	2699.768788	4	8632	7747.5
Human endocrine and metabolic diseases	15269.6	9060.755980	9	30101	15339.0
Human gastrointestinal diseases	5779.2	2715.341959	3	8755	6391.0
Human immunological diseases	5367.4	2335.513467	2	7613	6048.5
Human infectious diseases	14375.4	6367.805923	20	22693	14684.5
Human musculoskeletal diseases	2732.6	1102.783367	2	4053	2917.0
Human nervous and mental diseases	21840.2	9270.546679	11	35493	22244.0
Human respiratory diseases	2638.7	1325.384728	14	5243	2534.0
Human sensory organ diseases	9232.4	5416.482955	3	16921	8657.0
Human urogenital reproductive system diseases	1911.6	682.451008	944	3142	1848.5
Non regulatory toxicology and ecotoxicology	5045.6	3483.832857	5	10369	6191.5
Other human diseases	869.6	1198.524667	0	3961	476.0
Plant diseases	8.4	6.736303	0	22	10.0

Figure S4. Normality evaluation: histograms and q-q plots of animal uses across disease models in Spain (2014–2023).

Histogram: Human Cancer

Q-Q Plot: Human Cancer

Histogram: Infectious diseases

Q-Q Plot: Infectious diseases

Histogram: Cardiovascular diseases

Q-Q Plot: Cardiovascular diseases

Histogram: Nervous and mental diseases

Q-Q Plot: Nervous and mental diseases

Histogram: Human respiratory diseases

Q-Q Plot: Human respiratory diseases

Histogram: Gastrointestinal diseases

Q-Q Plot: Gastrointestinal diseases

Histogram: Musculoskeletal diseases

Q-Q Plot: Musculoskeletal diseases

Histogram: Immunological diseases

Q-Q Plot: Immunological diseases

Histogram: Urogenital reproductive system diseases

Q-Q Plot: Urogenital reproductive system diseases

Histogram: Sensory organ diseases

Q-Q Plot: Sensory organ diseases

Histogram: Endocrine and metabolic diseases

Q-Q Plot: Endocrine and metabolic disease

Histogram: Other human diseases

Q-Q Plot: Other human diseases

Histogram: Animal diseases

Q-Q Plot: Animal diseases

Histogram: Animal welfare

Q-Q Plot: Animal welfare

Histogram: Disease diagnosis

Q-Q Plot: Disease diagnosis

Histogram: Plant diseases

Q-Q Plot: Plant diseases

Histogram: Toxicology and ecotoxicology

Q-Q Plot: Toxicology and ecotoxicology

Table S8. Significant post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Dunn’s test with Bonferroni correction, assessing differences in animal use across years in disease models in Spain (2014–2023).

group1	group2	statistic	p	p.adj	p.adj. signif
2014	2015	4.458359024	8.258949e-06	3.716527e-04	***
2014	2016	4.528048106	5.953103e-06	2.678896e-04	***
2014	2017	4.646519545	3.375822e-06	1.519120e-04	***
2014	2018	4.763248758	1.905008e-06	8.572534e-05	****
2014	2019	4.939213690	7.843822e-07	3.529720e-05	****
2014	2020	4.583799372	4.566024e-06	2.054711e-04	***
2014	2021	4.623870594	3.766449e-06	1.694902e-04	***
2014	2022	4.775444347	1.793109e-06	8.068989e-05	****
2014	2023	4.651746227	3.291360e-06	1.481112e-04	***

Table S9. Significant post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Dunn’s test with Bonferroni correction, assessing differences in animal use across disease model categories in Spain (2014–2023).

group1	group2	statistic	p	p.adj	p.adj. signif
Animal diseases	Human musculoskeletal diseases	-4.17744694	2.947994e-05	4.009272e-03	**
Animal diseases	Human respiratory diseases	-4.20924915	2.562207e-05	3.484602e-03	**
Animal diseases	Human urogenital reproductive system diseases	-4.61131990	4.001202e-06	5.441635e-04	***
Animal diseases	Other human diseases	-5.18603120	2.148228e-07	2.921591e-05	****
Animal diseases	Plant diseases	-6.00153063	1.954661e-09	2.658338e-07	****
Animal welfare	Other human diseases	-3.93211564	8.420154e-05	1.145141e-02	*
Animal welfare	Plant diseases	-4.74761507	2.058293e-06	2.799278e-04	***
Human Cancer	Human musculoskeletal diseases	-4.24105135	2.224752e-05	3.025663e-03	**
Human Cancer	Human respiratory diseases	-4.27285356	1.929872e-05	2.624626e-03	**
Human Cancer	Human urogenital reproductive	-4.67492431	2.940621e-06	3.999244e-04	***

	e system diseases				
Human Cancer	Other human diseases	-5.24963561	1.524004e-07	2.072645e-05	****
Human Cancer	Plant diseases	-6.06513504	1.318428e-09	1.793062e-07	****
Human endocrine and metabolic diseases	Other human diseases	-3.89577026	9.788714e-05	1.331265e-02	*
Human endocrine and metabolic diseases	Plant diseases	-4.71126969	2.461782e-06	3.348024e-04	***
Human infectious diseases	Other human diseases	-3.94347357	8.030985e-05	1.092214e-02	*
Human infectious diseases	Plant diseases	-4.75897300	1.945805e-06	2.646294e-04	***
Human nervous and mental diseases	Human urogenital reproductive system diseases	-3.92530088	8.662140e-05	1.178051e-02	*
Human nervous and mental diseases	Other human diseases	-4.50001218	6.794957e-06	9.241142e-04	***
Human nervous and mental diseases	Plant diseases	-5.31551161	1.063581e-07	1.446470e-05	****
Human sensory organ diseases	Plant diseases	-3.75266033	1.749679e-04	2.379563e-02	*

Table S10. Descriptive statistics of animal species used in Spain before and after COVID-19.

Specie	Period	Mean	SD
Cats	Post-COVID	823.5000	142.1959
Cats	Pre-COVID	353.3333	181.1206
Cephalopods	Post-COVID	2588.5000	2337.0036
Cephalopods	Pre-COVID	8297.8333	6760.1555
Dogs	Post-COVID	1232.2500	341.5683
Dogs	Pre-COVID	1136.8333	288.5047
Mice	Post-COVID	443881.0000	29231.8276
Mice	Pre-COVID	499562.3333	32924.8694
Pigs	Post-COVID	10427.5000	1823.1885
Pigs	Pre-COVID	9462.3333	1340.2174

Poultry	Post-COVID	118852.5000	14210.6808
Poultry	Pre-COVID	80623.5000	23564.7818
Rabbits	Post-COVID	17826.2500	3273.4387
Rabbits	Pre-COVID	25408.1667	3826.0078
Sheep	Post-COVID	1824.0000	237.3703
Sheep	Pre-COVID	2394.0000	511.6311

Figure S5. Normality assessment: histograms and q-q plots of animal species used in Spain before and after COVID-19.

Table S11. Wilcoxon test with Bonferroni correction assessing differences in animal species used in Spain before and after COVID-19.

Specie	group1	group2	p	p.adj
Cats	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.00952	0.11424
Rabbits	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.01900	0.22800
Sheep	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.03810	0.45720
Mice	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.06670	0.80040
Crab-eating Macaques	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.11400	1.00000
Guinea Pig	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.11400	1.00000
Hamsters (Syrian)	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.17100	1.00000
Zebra Fish	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.17100	1.00000
Dogs	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.35200	1.00000
Pigs	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.35200	1.00000
Rhesus Macaques	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.53600	1.00000
Other Fish	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.91400	1.00000

Table S12. Wilcoxon test with Benjamini-Hochberg correction assessing differences in animal species used in Spain before and after COVID-19.

Specie	group1	group2	p	p.adj
Cats	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.00952	0.1140000
Rabbits	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.01900	0.1140000
Sheep	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.03810	0.1524000
Mice	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.06670	0.2001000
Crab-eating Macaques	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.11400	0.2280000
Guinea Pig	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.11400	0.2280000
Hamsters (Syrian)	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.17100	0.2565000
Zebra Fish	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.17100	0.2565000
Dogs	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.35200	0.4224000
Pigs	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.35200	0.4224000
Rhesus Macaques	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.53600	0.5847273
Other Fish	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.91400	0.9140000

Table S13. Descriptive statistics of animal used in the European Union before and after COVID-19.

Specie	Period	Mean	SD
Cats	Post-COVID	1964.667	529.75120
Cats	Pre-COVID	1905.400	223.64101
Cynomolgus monkey	Post-COVID	4639.000	376.79305
Cynomolgus monkey	Pre-COVID	6863.600	561.03012
Dogs	Post-COVID	9186.000	820.13353
Dogs	Pre-COVID	14931.600	1837.82774
Guinea-Pigs	Post-COVID	101722.000	14384.91484
Guinea-Pigs	Pre-COVID	138730.800	13989.66224
Hamsters (Syrian)	Post-COVID	22211.333	5181.47492
Hamsters (Syrian)	Pre-COVID	14866.400	4234.40802
Mice	Post-COVID	3992618.333	105035.95963
Mice	Pre-COVID	5659798.200	230677.51309
Other fish	Post-COVID	1015239.000	788475.51611
Other fish	Pre-COVID	1358153.600	752373.99677
Pigs	Post-COVID	79551.333	6824.30394
Pigs	Pre-COVID	78247.600	5314.88135
Rabbits	Post-COVID	357382.667	14384.81499
Rabbits	Pre-COVID	348796.600	4244.99898
Rats	Post-COVID	657896.667	29175.69438
Rats	Pre-COVID	1094968.000	110441.96845
Rhesus monkey	Post-COVID	215.000	69.77822
Rhesus monkey	Pre-COVID	290.600	57.90769
Sheep	Post-COVID	16349.333	995.43977
Sheep	Pre-COVID	20776.800	1360.21642
Zebra fish	Post-COVID	326697.667	44164.35681
Zebra fish	Pre-COVID	463774.000	72632.88198

Figure S6. Normality assessment: histograms and q-q plots of animal usage in the European Union before and after COVID-19.

Table S14. Wilcoxon test with Bonferroni correction assessing differences in animal species used in the European Union: Pre- and Post-COVID-19.

Specie	group1	group2	p	p.adj
Cynomolgus monkey	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.0357	0.4641
Dogs	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.0357	0.4641
Guinea-Pigs	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.0357	0.4641
Mice	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.0357	0.4641
Rats	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.0357	0.4641
Sheep	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.0357	0.4641
Hamsters (Syrian)	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.1430	1.0000
Zebra fish	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.1430	1.0000
Other fish	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.2500	1.0000
Rhesus monkey	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.2500	1.0000
Rabbits	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.3930	1.0000
Cats	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.7860	1.0000
Pigs	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	1.0000	1.0000

Table S15. Wilcoxon test with Benjamini-Hochberg correction assessing differences in animal species used in the European Union: Pre- and Post-COVID-19.

Specie	group1	group2	p	p.adj
Cynomolgus monkey	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.0357	0.0773500
Dogs	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.0357	0.0773500
Guinea-Pigs	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.0357	0.0773500
Mice	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.0357	0.0773500
Rats	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.0357	0.0773500
Sheep	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.0357	0.0773500
Hamsters (Syrian)	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.1430	0.2323750

Zebra fish	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.1430	0.2323750
Other fish	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.2500	0.3250000
Rhesus monkey	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.2500	0.3250000
Rabbits	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.3930	0.4644545
Cats	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	0.7860	0.8515000
Pigs	Post-COVID	Pre-COVID	1.0000	1.0000000